

Microporous Electrode Binders for Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzers

Hamza Khalid, Michaela Plevová, Trung Tuyen Bui, Malikah Najibah, Jaromír Hnát,*
Karel Bouzek, and Dirk Henkensmeier*

In anion exchange membrane (AEM) water electrolyzers, AEMs separate hydrogen and oxygen, but should efficiently transport hydroxide ions. In the electrodes, catalyst nanoparticles are mechanically bonded to the porous transport layer or membrane by a polymeric binder. Since these binders form a thin layer on the catalyst particles, they should not only transport hydroxide ions and water to the catalyst particles, but should also transport the nascent gases away. In the worst case, if formation of gases is \gg than gas transport, a gas pocket between catalyst surface and the binder may form and hinder access to reactants (hydroxide ions, water). In this work, the ion conductive binder SEBS-DABCO is blended with PIM-1, a highly permeable polymer of intrinsic microporosity. With increasing amount of PIM-1 in the blends, the permeability for water (selected to represent small molecules) increases. Simultaneously, swelling and conductivity decrease, due to the increased hydrophobicity. Ex situ data and electrochemical data indicate that blends with 50% PIM-1 have better properties than blends with 25% or 75% PIM-1, and tests in the electrolyzer confirm an improved performance when the SEBS-DABCO binder contains 50% PIM-1.

1. Introduction

Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzers (AEMWE) combine the advantages of traditional Alkaline Water Electrolyzers and Proton Exchange Membrane WE (PEMWE): The alkaline conditions allow use of non-noble catalysts, while the dense membrane reduces crossover of gases and can result in a low cell resistance, if the membrane has high conductivity, low thickness and is used in zero-gap cell designs.^[1] In combination, low hydrogen crossover and low cell resistance broaden the operational current range, which facilitates the operation of these systems with intermittent renewable energy sources.

Key components of AEMWE are the AEM,^[2] the catalysts, and the ionomer binder,^[3] which simultaneously holds the catalyst nanoparticles in place and provides an ion conducting connection between membrane and catalyst particles (Figure 1c). A high conductivity of the binder is wanted, and can be achieved by increasing

the ion exchange capacity (IEC). However, ionomer binders with high IEC also have a large swelling and are highly plasticized, and catalyst particles tend to be washed out during electrolyzer operation.^[4]

It is generally assumed that the ionomer binder covers the particles in the catalyst electrode with a thin film. This film can be either in direct contact with the catalyst particles, or, if a particle is located in one of the mesopores of a supported catalyst (e.g., platinum on carbon), it can cover the pore opening. In both cases, mass transport to and from the catalytically active site is only possible through the thin polymer film. This adds a design parameter: While ion conducting membranes should show low permeability to avoid crossover of hydrogen and oxygen, the ionomer binder should show a high permeability. Earlier work on fuel cells showed that ionomer binders based on perfluorinated Nafion often result in better fuel cell performance than binders based on sulfonated hydrocarbon polymers. A main reason is the roughly ten times lower oxygen permeability of polysulfones in comparison to Nafion.^[5,6] At high current density, mass transfer to the catalyst sites can be limited by the diffusion of oxygen through the ionomer binder. In that case, the *iV* curves of PEM fuel cells deviate from the linear ohmic behavior. Furthermore, if catalytically active sites are not accessible for the reaction partners, for

H. Khalid, T. T. Bui, M. Najibah, D. Henkensmeier
Hydrogen-Fuel Cell Research Center
Korea Institute of Science and Technology
Seoul 02792, Republic of Korea
E-mail: henkensmeier@kist.re.kr

H. Khalid, M. Najibah, D. Henkensmeier
Division of Energy & Environment Technology
KIST School
University of Science and Technology
Seoul 02792, Republic of Korea

M. Plevová, J. Hnát, K. Bouzek
Department of Inorganic Technology
University of Chemistry and Technology
Prague
166 28 Prague 6 Czech Republic
E-mail: Jaromir.Hnat@vscht.cz

D. Henkensmeier
Green School
Korea University
Seoul 02841, Republic of Korea

 The ORCID identification number(s) for the author(s) of this article can be found under <https://doi.org/10.1002/smll.202401592>

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Figure 1. a) Structure of SEBS-DABCO and b) PIM-1, c) schematic of membrane and ionomer-coated catalyst particles, d) HER at the catalytically active site, e) and limited access to water when the produced hydrogen forms a pocket between ionomer binder and catalyst surface.

example by cathode flooding, the utilization of the catalyst decreases, and with that usually also the performance.^[7] While it is possible to synthesize ionomer binders that have a more porous structure than standard ionomer binders, for example by building in kinked or bulky monomers,^[6,8] it is also possible to simply blend the ion conducting polymer with a highly permeable polymer. For example, Hutapea et al. blended Nafion and poly[1-phenyl-2-[p(trimethylsilyl)phenyl]acetylene].^[9]

Research on AEMWE so far did not much focus on this aspect, even though the ionomer binder needs to be highly permeable to transport water to the catalyst surface, and hydrogen away (Figure 1d). Different from fuel cells, it appears that a sudden, strong voltage increase by mass transfer limited overpotentials is seldom in AEMWE, but a slight deviation can be noticed for some systems.^[10–12] The absence of a strong, sudden voltage increase could be related to the fact that the hydrophilic domains of the polymers are highly swollen in contact with 50–60 °C warm liquid water, and that gases are transported across membranes as dissolved gases through these strongly swollen domains.^[1]

However, when bipolar membranes are operated so that water is produced at the interface of the PEM and AEM layers (by combination of protons and hydroxide ions), the two layers delaminate and may blister or balloon when the production rate of water exceeds the diffusion rate of water.^[13,14] Similarly, on a local scale, if transport of gases away from the AEMWE catalyst is slower than the gas formation (Figure 1e), the produced gases must form a gas-filled pocket between the catalyst and the ionomer binder film. Even if this pocket would be microscopically small, it would destroy the interface between catalyst and the ion conducting polymer, and should reduce the accessibility and thus utilization of the catalyst particles.

To look into the effect of the ionomer binder's gas permeability, Fu et al. synthesized a poly(phenyl-alkane) with a spirobisindane group in the backbone.^[15] Hu et al. synthesized a rigid poly(aryl-

co-aryl piperidinium) that includes a spirobisindane moiety and achieved a new current density record of 13.39 and 10.7 A cm⁻² with and without PGM anode catalysts, respectively.^[16] Lee et al. reported a highly crosslinked membrane consisting of a spirobisindane-containing polymer and a SEBS-based AEM. The membrane was alkaline stable, and retained 98% of its conductivity in 1 M KOH at 80 °C, but the material's insolubility prevents its use as binder.^[17] We selected a more simple and broadly applicable approach to increase the ionomer binder's permeability, and blended a well-known ionomer binder (SEBS-DABCO,^[18,19] Figure 1a) with PIM-1, a polymer of intrinsic microporosity (Figure 1b),^[20,21] which has up to 2000 times higher oxygen permeability than Nafion,^[6] and, during preparation of this manuscript, was suggested as a binder in alkaline systems, based on ex situ data obtained with rotating disc electrodes.^[22] Our expectation is that addition of PIM-1 increases permeability and decreases conductivity, and that an optimized blend ratio can improve the AEMWE performance.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. PIM-1 / SEBS-DABCO Blends: Material Properties

Blend membranes of SEBS-DABCO and PIM-1 were prepared by co-casting PIM-1 and chloromethylated SEBS into a membrane, followed by heterogeneous quaternization with DABCO. The membranes were transparent (Figure S1, Supporting Information), indicating that the blends were homogeneous, and SEM images did not reveal any phase separation (Figure S2, Supporting Information). The density of the membranes strongly increased when SEBS-DABCO was added to PIM-1, and then linearly decreased again from 75% over 50% and 25% to pure SEBS-DABCO (Figure S3, Supporting Information). The reason is that PIM-1 and chloromethylated SEBS are both hydrophobic

Figure 2. Mechanical properties.

and blend well, so that the free volume of PIM-1 is lost. After quaternization, the blended structure should hinder efficient microphase separation into clearly separated hydrophilic and hydrophobic domains. In contact with water, the quaternary ammonium groups are hydrated, and the PIM-1 and SEBS-DABCO polymer chains presumably get more separated from each other. This would result in a rather narrow but well-connected water-containing phase.

The mechanical properties of the blend materials continuously change with increasing amount of PIM-1. Pure SEBS-DABCO had a very low tensile strength of 2.4 MPa, it was very flexible and showed an elongation at break of 366% (Figure 2). Addition of PIM-1 slightly increased the tensile strength and strongly decreased the elongation at break up to 50% PIM-1, whereas blends with 75% PIM-1 lost all flexibility (5.2% elongation at break) and became noticeably stronger (tensile strength of 19.6 MPa, Young's Modulus of 489 MPa). Pure PIM-1 membranes had a tensile strength of 24.5 MPa, Young's Modulus of 826 MPa, and showed an elongation at break of 4.7%. For comparison, the tensile strength of Nafion and FAA3-50 were reported to be 22 and 12 MPa, respectively, while the Young's Modulus was 224 and 511 MPa, respectively, and the elongation at break was 188% and 34%, respectively.^[23] In conclusion, addition of PIM-1 allows to optimize the mechanical properties, and blends with 50–75% PIM-1 have similar tensile strength as well-known commercial membranes.

In the electrolyzer, the ion-conducting polymers are in contact with KOH solution. Addition of PIM-1 to the blends not only decreases the elongation at break, it also decreases the uptake of KOH solution at 60 °C (Figure 3c). The same trend is observed also for length and thickness swelling, which decreases as well when the ratio of PIM-1 to SEBS-DABCO is increased. The main reason is that PIM-1 is a hydrophobic polymer, it absorbs a small amount of KOH solution into its pores, but has no strong interaction with water. The strongest interaction is that between water and the dipolar nitrile groups, while SEBS-DABCO has very strong interactions between its quaternary ammonium groups and hydroxide ions and water. When the temperature is increased from 30 to 60 °C, both length and thickness swelling increase, but with a preference of the thickness direction. Such anisotropic behavior is often observed in membranes, and may be even more

Figure 3. Weight gain, length, and thickness swelling in 1 M KOH.

Figure 4. Transport properties: a) water vapor/vapor crossover, measured at 60 °C and a concentration gradient of 100% rh to 50% rh, b) ion conductivity.

pronounced for very thin films deposited on catalyst surfaces. The very low length swelling of 5.0% and 3.2% for blends with 50% and 75% PIM-1 even at 60 °C is advantageous for the use as ionomer binder, because large area swelling and shrinking would facilitate delamination.

As already discussed in the introduction, the cathode reaction consumes water, and the ionomer binder should be highly permeable for it. Furthermore, gas transport is assumed to be via dissolved gas molecules through water filled volumes in the polymer binder. In this sense, the most important property is the water permeation. While there is no simple ex situ method for measuring hydrogen crossover, the vapor/vapor-permeation of water is easily accessible.^[23–25] Glass bottles are filled with water and closed with caps having a hole, which is covered by a piece of membrane. When these bottles are stored in a climate chamber, the temperature inside and outside the bottle is same, while the atmosphere inside is water saturated and outside has the controlled relative humidity of the set value. Weight loss of the bottles is monitored over time, and caused by vapor/vapor permeation through the membranes.

Figure 4a shows that the water vapor/vapor-crossover increases noticeably from $268 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mmol cm s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for SEBS-

Table 1. Comparison of the conductivities of the catalyst's layers composed of different polymer blends.

SEBS-DABCO / PIM-1 [% PIM-1]	Electrical conductivity [mS m^{-1}]	Total conductivity [mS m^{-1}]
0	12.0 ± 0.04	1330 ± 459
25	3.4 ± 0.17	5.6 ± 1.6
50	1.3 ± 0.21	2.3 ± 0.7

DABCO to 421 and $552 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mmol cm s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for the blend membranes with 50% and 75% PIM-1, respectively. At the same time, the decreased uptake of KOH solution decreases the conductivity from 60 mS cm^{-1} for SEBS-DABCO at 30 °C to 25 and 17 mS cm^{-1} for the blends with 50% and 75% PIM-1, respectively (Figure 4b). Data for PIM-1 is not shown, because it showed a very low conductivity. The activation energy of the ion conduction varied around 20 kJ mol^{-1} , and showed values of 16.2, 23.4, 23.9, and 21.9 for blends with 0%, 25%, 50%, and 75% PIM-1 (Figure S4, Supporting Information). This is similar to reported values for Fumatech's FAA3-PK-75 (25.3) and PI-15 and PI-20 AEMs from Versogen ($22.5\text{--}25.2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$).^[23] In conclusion, conductivity and permeability are in a trade-off relation for the series of blend materials, and the materials need to be further analyzed by electrochemical methods to find the optimum blend composition.

For testing the alkaline stability, samples were immersed in 1 M KOH at 60 °C for up to 1 month. In between, samples were removed from the solution, washed with water to remove access KOH, and the in-plane hydroxide conductivity was measured. CO_2 was excluded by electrochemically purging carbonates from the membrane.^[23] Interestingly, the pure SEBS-DABCO membrane was most stable, and the resistance increased with increasing amount of PIM-1 in the blends (Figure 5). Presumably, PIM-1 increases the unselective absorption of KOH solution and thus the local pH in the membrane, which accelerates alkaline degradation of the DABCO groups. This is most pronounced for the membrane with 75% PIM-1. In this light, the blend with 50% PIM-1 seems to balance the different properties (conductivity, water crossover, alkaline stability, mechanical properties) in the best way (Figure 5).

2.2. Use as Ionomer Binder

Results of catalyst layer conductivity measurements are shown in Table 1. It can be seen that electrical conductivity of the layer is small and probably represents the bottleneck of the catalyst-coated membrane approach. Combining the pure CM-SEBS binder with PIM-1 polymer resulted in additional decrease of the electrical conductivity. After functionalization of the CM-SEBS, mixed (total) conductivity of the catalyst layer increased.

Table 1 clearly shows that conductivity values may represent limitation of the catalyst-coated membrane approach due to low ability to transport charge either in the form of electrons or ions. The highest values of electrical and total conductivity were achieved using pure SEBS-DABCO polymer binder. Increasing the content of PIM-1, both electrical and total conductivity decreased. This is not surprising for the case of the total

Figure 5. Alkaline stability in 1 M KOH at 60 °C: Conductivity and resistance were measured in-plane after cooling to room temperature and washing in water.

conductivity as the highest value was achieved due the presence of the pure anion-conductive phase. This result is in agreement with the results shown in Figure 4b. Explanation of the electrical conductivity decrease is not so straightforward. The reason lies in the fact that electrical conductivity of the catalyst layer is established by catalyst particles (NiCo_2O_4 powder conductivity 3600 mS m^{-1})^[26] and can be influenced by the content of the polymer binder and/or morphology of the catalyst layer. However, the total amount of the polymer in the catalyst layer was the same for all samples (catalyst to polymer binder ratio 80:20). The observed differences thus resulted from differences in the morphology of the catalyst layers. The influence of the polymer binder on the morphology was observed on swelling of the prepared catalyst layers. The thicknesses of the catalyst layers after swelling were 71, 23, and 11 μm for SEBS-DABCO / PIM-1 0%, 25% and 50% PIM-1, respectively. The dry thickness of all samples was the same (10 μm). Increasing amount of the PIM-1 thus reduces the swelling of the catalyst layer, which is once more in agreement

Table 2. Overview of the Tafel parameters comparing the activity of different catalyst layers.

SEBS-DABCO / PIM-1 [% PIM-1]	j_0 [A cm^{-2}]	b [V dec^{-1}]	$\eta_{0.01}$ [V]
0	2.3×10^{-7}	0.062	0.348
25	4.4×10^{-7}	0.078	0.352
50	1.6×10^{-8}	0.056	0.344

with the results of the pure polymer blend (Figure 3C). In order to gain deeper information on the catalyst layer morphology SEM analysis of the catalyst layer surfaces has been used.

SEM images of the surface of the catalyst layers are shown in Figure 6. In the case of 50% PIM-1 & 50% CM-PSEBS more frequent and smaller disturbances of the catalyst layer surface have been observed. Additionally, more frequent disturbances in the catalyst layer surface can explain even the differences in electrical conductivity of the catalyst layer. To provide more complex information on electrochemical performance of the catalyst layers with different polymer binders, RDE measurement was performed.

There is a significant difference between RDE and conductivity measurements. As oxygen is produced during RDE, even the permeability of the layer for gases plays an important role. Measured polarization curves and the corresponding Tafel lines are shown in Figure 7. It is seen from the polarization curve measurement that the sample with 50% PIM-1 showed the best activity at current densities up to 54 mA cm^{-2} (calculated from the linear trend lines of data between 30 and 90 mA cm^{-2}).

The values extracted from the Tafel analysis are summarized in Table 2. The three parameters used to describe the catalyst layer activity are j_0 , b , and $\eta_{0.01}$. j_0 represents the current density achieved under equilibrium conditions. A higher j_0 suggests higher catalytic activity, due to the faster charge transport across the phase boundary at equilibrium conditions. Parameter b stands for the slope of the linear part of the Tafel curve (Figure 7b) and is commonly called Tafel slope. Its value is connected with the rate-limiting step in the complex mechanism of the oxygen evolution. A lower value of the Tafel slope means a lower potential increase with increasing current density. The last parameter $\eta_{0.01}$ combines the influence of j_0 and b through the equation $\eta = b \log(\frac{j}{j_0})$. Parameter η represents the driving force of the reaction and is obviously dependent on the current density. From this reason, for purposes of comparison, it was evaluated for all samples at the same current density of 0.01 A cm^{-2} .

The lowest value of $\eta_{0.01}$, indicating the highest activity, was observed for the sample containing 50% PIM-1, which had an overpotential of 0.344 V at 0.01 A cm^{-2} . This was obviously due to the positive effect of the lowest parameter b . On the other hand, the same sample showed the lowest (the worst) value of the j_0 . The low value of j_0 can be connected with low electrical conductivity of the catalyst layer with 50% PIM-1 (Table 1), since it is necessary to establish electrical contact for catalyst particles to be active. The parameter b is connected with the reaction mechanism and processes taking place under the current load. The lowest value of b thus indicates a positive effect of the 50% PIM-1 on the properties of the catalyst layer under the current load.

Figure 6. SEM pictures of the surface of prepared catalyst layers with different binders. The red circles indicate regions with small pore-like disturbances.

Based on the RDE results, the catalyst layer containing the polymer binder CM-SEBS / PIM-1 (50% PIM-1) was selected for the use in an anion exchange membrane water electrolyzer single cell.

2.3. Electrolyzer Performance

A catalyst coated membrane was prepared with NiCo_2O_4 anode catalyst and NiFe_2O_4 cathode catalyst. The catalyst load was 2.5 mg cm^{-2} and the catalyst to binder ratio was 93/7. 50% PIM-1 & 50% CM-SEBS ratio was used. This combination showed the lowest electrode conductivity in ex situ tests, but at the same time showed the lowest overpotential and higher water permeability than 25% PIM-1 & 75% CM-SEBS. Results in the form of the load curves are shown in **Figure 8a**. It is seen from **Figure 8** that the addition of PIM-1 led to improved performance with both KOH feed solutions (0.1 M and 1 M KOH). At the same time, the higher KOH concentration resulted in improved performance and a reduced difference between pure SEBS-DABCO and SEBS-DABCO / PIM-1 50% samples. Electro-

chemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analysis was performed in order to obtain more information on the system. Results of EIS are shown in **Figure 8b–d**.

Figure 8b–d shows that in 0.1 M KOH solution the CCM with 50% PIM-1 showed lower values of ohmic resistance (R_s) and of the polarization resistances (R_{p1} and R_{p2}). With 1 M KOH feed solution, ohmic resistance and polarization resistances are comparable for both tested samples. This observation is in agreement with the results of the load curve.

The lower resistances of the CCM with 50% PIM-1 in 0.1 M KOH solution can be caused by its higher porosity as the reactants and/or products can penetrate through the catalyst layer more easily. The effect of penetration of the liquid electrolyte into the bulk of the catalyst layer is more important when OH^- ions are less available, that is, at low KOH concentration. This is due to the fact that OH^- from the liquid solution improves ionic contact within the catalyst layer, increasing thus its conductivity and utilization of the catalyst particles at the same time. When higher KOH concentration is used, the effect of the catalyst layer porosity is lowered by the high amount of OH^- present in the system.

Figure 7. Polarisation a) and Tafel b) curves measured for polymer binders containing 0%, 25%, and 50% PIM-1.

Figure 8. Load curves of the alkaline water electrolysis using different polymer binders in the catalyst layers (a). Results of EIS analysis for b) Ohmic resistance and (c) and (d) Polarization resistances. Temperature was set to 50 °C, anode catalyst was NiCo₂O₄, cathode catalyst was NiFe₂O₄, catalyst load was 2.5 mg cm⁻², membrane was PSEBS-CM-DABCO. Catalyst to binder ratio was 93/7. Cell voltage was 1.8 V, the perturbing signal amplitude was 20 mV, the frequency range 20 kHz–0.1 Hz.

At the same time, all observed resistances (R_s , R_{p1} , and R_{p2}) are lower when using 1 M KOH solution, when compared to 0.1 M KOH. This is due to the improved conductivity of the system and the resulting higher utilization of the catalyst in the catalyst layer

as it was mentioned before. Additionally, the OH⁻ ions represent the reactant at the anode.

Figure 9 shows a 270 h stability test for a CCM made with 50 wt% PIM-1 and 50 wt% SEBS-DABCO as catalyst binder. The

Figure 9. a) Stability test of a CCM with 50 wt% PIM-1 in SEBS-DABCO/PIM-1 blend as catalyst binder. The temperature was set to 50 °C, 1 M KOH was used as circulating electrolyte, anode catalyst was NiCo₂O₄, cathode catalyst was NiFe₂O₄, catalyst load was 2.5 mg cm⁻², membrane was PSEBS-CM-DABCO. Catalyst to binder ratio was 93/7. b) For EIS, the cell voltage was 1.8 V, the perturbing signal amplitude was 20 mV, the frequency range 20 kHz–0.1 Hz.

initial and terminal cell voltages were 1.95 and 2.02 V, respectively, which equals a cell voltage increase of 0.28 mV h^{-1} . However, Figure 9 shows nice stability of the MEA for the first 190 h of operation. For the first 20 h of the experiment, a sharp increase of the cell voltage (2.0 mV h^{-1}) from 1.95 to 1.99 V is seen. This is due to the evolution of the gas phase and equilibration of cell components. If the first 20 h are omitted, the cell voltage increase between 20 and 190 h corresponds to 0.1 mV h^{-1} . On the other hand, cell voltage increase in the interval 190–270 h shows a rate of 0.21 mV h^{-1} . Clearly, the cell voltage increase is not linear, but it increases in steps, possibly because the system absorbed CO_2 . CO_2 has a negative impact on the conductivity of the liquid electrolyte, anion-selective binder and membrane, and the kinetics of the electrode reactions.^[27] Two sources of CO_2 can be considered. 1) The system was opened to the atmosphere and CO_2 from the air thus could react with KOH electrolyte. In this case, a linear influence can be expected. 2) Water lost by reaction and evaporation into the gas streams needs to be refilled. Due to the low loss rate, this is not done continuously, but at arbitrary intervals, and seems to be the reason for arbitrary step-wise increases of the cell voltage.

EIS measurements (Figure 9b) reveal possible reasons for the observed cell voltage changes. The serial resistance R_s , which is attributed to the ohmic resistance of the cell, shows a fluctuating behavior, and the flattening or decrease of the curve $\approx 260 \text{ h}$ does not correspond to chemical degradation behavior. A sine fit indicates that R_s fluctuates around the value of $0.33 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ with an amplitude of $0.07 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$. R_{p1} increased from 0.93 to $1.67 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$, which represents the main contribution to the cell voltage and its increase. Even more, as the R_{p1} value becomes the dominant source of the resistance, the value of R_{p2} is gradually less significant (one order of magnitude lower) and after 100 h became negligible. The increase of the R_{p1} value most probably is related to CO_2 contamination of the liquid electrolyte. This is supported by the drop at 220–260 h, which is not typical for material degradation.

After the stability test, cross-section SEM images revealed delamination of the cathode catalyst layer (Figure S6, Supporting Information). However, it is not possible to determine whether the delamination is a consequence of the stability test, happened when disassembling the cell, or when preparing the sample for SEM analysis.

From the SEM images in Figure 10, which were taken after the tests shown in Figure 8, it is possible to see that the anode catalyst layer appearance depends on the binder. Using the binder with 50% PIM-1, the layer is less homogeneous compared to the layer with only CM-SEBS binder. In both cases, the layers did not change significantly after the electrolysis test, which indicates good stability. The situation is quite different with the cathode catalyst layer. Using the 50% PIM-1 binder, a pore-like structure appeared, which was a little bit visible in Figure 6. This structure is desirable when the ionomer binder's permeability should be increased. On the other hand, this structure probably causes the low conductivity of the catalyst layer with addition of PIM-1. But, as the performance in alkaline water electrolysis increased, especially in the low concentration environment, the improved permeability of the binder seems to be the important parameter of the catalyst layer.

3. Conclusion

SEBS-DABCO is a well-investigated ionomer binder, which typically is quaternized after the CCM has been formed. This facilitates blending of the precursor polymer CM-SEBS with PIM-1, which are both soluble in organic solvents like chloroform.

Membranes made of SEBS-DABCO/PIM-1 blends showed an increasing tensile strength when the amount of PIM-1 is increased. As expected, addition of hydrophobic PIM-1 reduces the swelling in contact with water, which potentially improves the durability of the catalyst layer. At the same time, addition of PIM-1 decreases the ionic conductivity, but increases the water permeability.

Alkaline stability in 1 M KOH at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was tested, and indicated that pure SEBS-DABCO and blends with 25% and 50% PIM-1 have a reasonably high stability, whereas the blend with 75% PIM-1 showed a noticeable onset of degradation.

The ex situ analysis of blend membranes indicated that the blend with 50% PIM-1 balances the different properties (conductivity, water crossover, alkaline stability, mechanical properties) in the best way.

Characterization of SEBS-DABCO/PIM-1 blends in the form of the catalyst layer revealed the significance of the catalyst layer porosity, which controls the permeation of gasses. Ex situ measurements of the catalyst layer's electronic and total combined ionic and electronic conductivities showed a negative effect of the PIM-1 addition. However, under the operating conditions of an AEMWE, a cell with 50% SEBS-DABCO/50% PIM-1 blend as binder showed better performance compared to a cell with pure SEBS-DABCO ionomer binder. This was even more significant in highly diluted KOH solution due to the improved contact of the catalyst particles with OH^- ions.

In summary, this work supports that the very recent trend to investigate the ionomer binder porosity for AEMWE is a valid strategy to improve the AEMWE performance.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: (PSEBS) Polystyrene-*block*-poly(ethylene-*ran*-butylene)-*block*-polystyrene (powder, $M_w = 118,000 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$ by GPC, contains $>0.03\%$ antioxidants), dimethoxymethane (DMOM) ($\geq 99\%$), phosphorus trichloride PCl_3 (99%), zinc chloride anhydrous (ZnCl_2), potassium chloride (KCl) and potassium iodide (KI) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Potassium carbonate (anhydrous, 99%), *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF, 99.9%), chloroform ($\geq 99.5\%$), ethanol ($\geq 99.9\%$), methanol ($\geq 99.9\%$), KOH flakes and sodium chloride (NaCl) were purchased from Daejung Chemicals. Tetrafluoroterephthalonitrile (TFTPN, 98%), 5,5',6,6'-tetrahydroxy-3,3',3'-tetramethyl-1,1'-spirobisindane (TTSBI, 96%), 1,4-diazabicyclo[2.2.2]octane (DABCO) were purchased from Tokyo Chemical Industry (TCI). All these reagents were used as received without any modifications.

Synthesis of PIM-1: PIM-1 was synthesized using a low-temperature polycondensation reaction of TFTPN and TTSBI, following a previously reported method.^[28–30] All glassware was dried at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in an oven before use, and then flushed with argon. Equimolar amounts of TFTPN (3.00 g, 15.0 mmol) and TTSBI (5.11 g, 15.0 mmol) were dissolved in dry DMF (100 mL) at room temperature in a 250 mL three necked flask. The flask was equipped with a mechanical stirrer for mixing the reaction mixture and an argon atmosphere was maintained during the reaction. Next, the reaction flask was immersed into a preheated $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ oil bath. Potassium carbonate (5.18 g, 37.5 mmol) was added to the warm solution, and the reaction was stirred under an argon atmosphere at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 72 h.

Figure 10. SEM images of the surface of prepared CCMs with different binders before and after the stability test under the conditions of the alkaline water electrolysis.

After completion of the reaction, the solution was cooled to room temperature, and the polymer was precipitated in 200 mL of water. The crude product was collected by filtration. The filtered polymer was rinsed with DI water to remove salts, then dissolved in chloroform (200 mL) and re-precipitated in methanol. The re-precipitated polymer was filtered and dried in a vacuum oven at 70 °C for three days to obtain pure PIM-1. The yield was 6.3 g (91%).

Chloromethylation of PSEBS (CM-PSEBS): All the glassware was dried in an oven at 60 °C prior to use. A 100 g solution of 5 wt% PSEBS (polystyrene-*block*-poly(ethylene-*ran*-butylene)-*block*-polystyrene) in chloroform was prepared in a 250 mL round bottom flask. Next, DMOM (0.138 mol), the chlorinating agent PCl_3 (0.0140 mol) and the catalyst ZnCl_2 (0.0140 mol) were added to the 5 wt% PSEBS.^[31] It took 1 h for the catalyst to be fully dissolved or dispersed in the solution and an argon atmosphere was maintained over the reaction mixture during this 1 h time. Gradually, the mixture changed color from transparent to light brownish within this time. Afterward, the mixture was heated to 60 °C and left to react for 48 h. Due to the close boiling point of chloroform

to the reaction temperature, a large reflux condenser was used. As the reaction progressed, the mixture gradually changed color and ultimately turned brown. After the 48-h reaction period, the mixture was diluted using chloroform in an equal volume ratio of 1:1 and then precipitated into an excess of ethanol. This led to the precipitation of chloromethylated PSEBS, which was separated by filtration and washed with ethanol. The presence of ethanol in the CM-PSEBS improved its solubility in chloroform. NMR analysis showed that the degree of chloromethylation was 57%.

Preparation of Membranes: Precisely 0.3 g of PIM-1 and CM-PSEBS were separately dissolved in 9.7 g of CHCl_3 , resulting in 3 wt% solutions of pristine PIM-1 (100%) and CM-PSEBS (100%). Blends of PIM-1 and CM-PSEBS were prepared by mixing the solutions in the ratios of 75% PIM-1 & 25% CM-PSEBS, 50% PIM-1 & 50% CM-PSEBS and 25% PIM-1 & 75% CM-PSEBS. Each casting solution was sonicated for 15 min at room temperature, followed by overnight magnetic stirring to ensure homogeneous mixing. Only CM-PSEBS membranes were cast on thick Teflon plates, to facilitate delamination. Petri dishes were covered with an aluminum foil with small holes for slow solvent evaporation. Thin films were obtained

after 48 h of gradual evaporation, and then further dried in an oven for an additional 4 h to eliminate the remaining solvent. The oven temperature gradually increased from RT to 60 °C at a rate of 15 °C h⁻¹. All the membranes were quaternized in a 10 wt% solution of DABCO in ethanol for 48 h. After the quaternization reaction, the membranes were washed with deionized (DI) water multiple times. To ensure even drying and prevent any potential wrinkling caused by non-uniform drying, tissue paper was placed between the membranes and two plastic foils. Subsequently, the membranes were activated using a 1 M KOH solution.

Mechanical Properties: Cometech QC-508E universal testing machine was used to measure the mechanical properties. Square-shaped samples of 4 cm in length and 1 cm in width were cut from the membranes. For every membrane a minimum of five samples were tested at a crosshead speed of 10 mm min⁻¹. Measurements were performed in ambient atmosphere at RT (27 °C) at 70%rh (rh = relative humidity). [31]

Alkaline Stability: To assess the chemical stability of the membranes against OH⁻ ions, 4 × 1 cm² stripes were cut from the membranes and quaternized in a 10 wt% solution of DABCO in ethanol for 48 h. Subsequently, they were immersed in a 1 M KOH (5.5 wt%) solution, placed in sealed polypropylene vials, and stored in an oven at 60 °C. To ensure consistent alkalinity, the solutions were refreshed every 7 days to prevent continuous CO₂ absorption. After 1, 3, 5, 7, 14, 21, and 28 days, the solutions were cooled to room temperature, and the samples were taken out and washed with DI water for ≈60 min. In-plane conductivity was then measured at room temperature, and the samples were immersed again in KOH solution to continue the stability test. At the end of the test, changes in the chemical structure due to alkaline degradation were investigated by FTIR spectroscopy (Lambda Scientific, FTIR 7600) with an ATR sample holder.

Swelling Ratio: Sample stripes of the size 4 cm × 1 cm² were quaternized and ion exchanged as described in section "Preparation of Membranes". A set of three samples for each membrane type was dried at 60 °C in the vacuum to get the dry length L_{dry} and thickness T_{dry}. Another set of samples was stored in 1 M KOH at RT for 24 h. After the 24-h period, the membranes were placed inside 1 M KOH filled vials and the temperature was incrementally increased from RT to 30, 40, 50, and 60 °C. At each temperature step, the membrane was allowed to equilibrate for 1 h, and the wet length (L_{wet}) was measured by transferring the samples into a petri dish containing 1 M KOH at the corresponding temperature. A photo of the sample inside the water, next to a ruler, was taken and analyzed using GIMP 2.0 software. Then the wet thickness T_{wet} was measured with a thickness gauge equipped with disc-shaped sensors (1 cm diameter). The swelling ratio (SR) of the membrane samples was calculated from the difference between the wet and dry dimensions.

$$\text{SR (length)} = \frac{L_{\text{wet}} - L_{\text{dry}}}{L_{\text{dry}}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

$$\text{SR (thickness)} = \frac{T_{\text{wet}} - T_{\text{dry}}}{T_{\text{dry}}} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

Conductivity: For in-plane conductivity measurement, samples were prepared as described in Section "Chloromethylation of PSEBS (CM-PSEBS)". However, for the activation of blend membranes, KCl was used instead of KOH, and excess KCl was removed after immersing membranes in DI water for 24 h. Wet membranes of (4 × 1 cm²) were assembled into a conductivity clamp (Wonatech) and in-plane conductivity was measured in DI water. Nitrogen was continuously bubbled through the water to remove carbonates. Every 30 min, electrochemical purging was stopped, and several linear voltage sweeps were conducted over the range of 100–100 mV with a scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹ until the resistance reached a constant value. Impedance spectroscopy (Zive SP1) was used to detect resistances, and conductivity was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{In-plane conductivity, } \sigma \text{ (mS cm}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{1000 \times d}{R_{\text{mem}} \times w \times t} \quad (3)$$

where d represents distance between the voltage sensing electrodes (cm), w is the width of membrane sample (cm), and t is membrane thickness after immersing in DI water (cm). Set value of d is 1 cm. R_{mem} is the membrane resistance (Ω)

Water Permeation: To measure water permeation, 20 mL glass vials were used, and a precise 6 mm diameter hole was drilled into the screw caps. A membrane was placed between the cap and the seal, covering the hole. The vials were filled with water, leaving a small headspace, and then placed in a climate chamber operating at 60 °C and 50% relative humidity (%rh). After 24 h of equilibration, the headspace inside the vials was assumed to be at 100%rh, and the weight loss was measured at 8 and 16-h intervals over a period of 3.5 days. For each type of membrane, three samples were tested simultaneously. The weight loss raw data showed a consistent linear trend with excellent correlation (R² > 0.999) for all membrane types.

Catalyst Layer Preparation and Conductivity Measurement: First, the as received PIM-1 was dissolved in chloroform to obtain a 5 wt% solution. This solution was then mixed with CM-SEBS (also 5 wt% solution) to obtain different composition of the binders: 75% PIM-1 & 25% CM-SEBS and 50% PIM-1 & 50% CM-SEBS. For comparison, pure CM-SEBS was used. NiCo₂O₄ oxygen evolution catalyst was used for preparation of the catalyst layer. Catalyst to binder ratio was 80:20 (mass) as 20 wt% of polymer corresponds to the minimum content allowing preparation of the self-standing layer. Catalyst layers were deposited on the PTFE sheet using sonicated dispersion deposition method. The sample was, during deposition, placed on a heated pad and heated to 50 °C to dry the layers. The PTFE sheet with the layer was weighted during deposition until the catalyst loading reached 2.5 mg cm⁻². After the layer was dry, it was peeled of the PTFE sheet and used for measurements. The area of the prepared layer was 5 × 1 cm². The samples were used as prepared for measuring electron conductivity. In the next step, samples were immersed in 10 wt% DABCO solution in ethanol for 24 h in order to introduce functional groups to the CM-SEBS polymer. Finally, samples were transferred to the OH⁻ form by immersion in 0.1 M NaOH solution prior to total conductivity measurement (ionic and electron conductivity).

The conductivity was measured at laboratory temperature in through-plane direction using a Hg-conductivity cell with circular active area of 15.7 mm². The sample was squeezed between two plastic boxes, which were consequently filled with Hg. Mercury was in contact with the measured sample providing thus electric contact. Solartron potentiostat and frequency analyzer were used to perform electrochemical impedance (EIS) measurements. The frequency range was 1 MHz–10 Hz. The maximum amplitude of the perturbing signal was 20 mV. The conductivity of the catalyst layers was calculated from the resistivity according to the formula $\sigma = \frac{d}{R \times S}$, where σ represents the ionic conductivity [S m⁻¹], d corresponds to the thickness of the measured sample [m], R is the measured resistance [Ω] and S stands for the area of the sample [m²].

Rotating Disc Electrode Measurements: NiCo₂O₄ catalyst was used for testing the polymer blends on a rotating disk electrode (RDE). Ten milligrams of catalyst powder was mixed with 10 μL of binder (75% PIM-1 & 25% CM-SEBS, 50% PIM-1 & 50% CM-SEBS, pure CM-SEBS) and 5 mL of ethylene glycol. The ink was then homogenized for 30 min in an ultrasound bath. A total amount of 20 μL of the ink was deposited on the RDE in two steps and let to dry. The last preparation step consisted in the RDE immersion in 10 wt% DABCO ethanol solution for 24 h to ensure the functionalization of the CM-SEBS binder in the layer. The electrochemical cell for RDE measurement was filled with 0.1 M KOH and heated to 30 °C. The rotation speed was 1000 rpm. Counter electrode was Ni wire, reference electrode was reversible hydrogen electrode and the area of the RDE was 0.196 cm².

The RDE was first activated by cycling voltammetry with 100 cycles followed by the linear sweep voltammetry in the potential range of 1.2–2.4 V with the potential sweep rate 0.01 V s⁻¹. The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy at 0 V was used to measure the resistance of the system to perform the IR correction. Tafel analysis of the measured polarization curve gave the values of exchange current density (j₀), Tafel slope (b), and overpotential at 0.01 A cm⁻² (η_{0.01}).

Membrane Alkaline Water Electrolysis: For alkaline water electrolysis test, the catalyst-coated membrane approach was used. The catalyst ink consisted of the catalyst powder (NiCo_2O_4 anode catalyst and NiFe_2O_4 cathode catalyst) that was mixed with the corresponding amount of polymer binder (50% PIM-1 & 50% CM-SEBS or just pure CM-SEBS) and solvent/dispersant (chloroform). Catalyst to binder ratio was 93/7 and the catalyst loading was 2.5 mg cm^{-2} . The prepared catalyst ink was sonicated for 10 min with Bandelin Sonoplus HD 2200 ultrasonic nozzle (power 30%).

The catalyst ink was applied to the membrane with an active area of $6 \times 6 \text{ cm}^2$ by computer-controlled ultrasonic dispersion deposition. After the catalyst layers were deposited the membrane was immersed in 10 wt% solution of DABCO in ethanol for 24 h at room temperature to functionalize the binder in the catalyst layer. Then the sample was washed with deionized water and immersed in 0.1 M NaOH solution for 24 h.

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) Hitachi S4700 (Japan) was used for investigating the morphology of the prepared CCMs. The samples were fixed on an aluminium pad by double-sided carbon adhesive tape. To obtain the cross-section, the dry sample was cut using a scalpel. Due to the low electron conductivity, the samples were coated with a conductive Au/Pd layer $\approx 20 \text{ nm}$ thick by vacuum sputtering.

For alkaline water electrolysis the membrane-electrode assembly (MEA) was prepared by pressing the Ni foam electrodes to the CCM with active area of $2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$. The MEA was placed in the cell, which consisted of two end plates made from duralumin and the cell body made from PEEK. The cell was sealed using a GORE GR 05 Teflon (WL Gore & Associates Inc.) sealing. Gold-plated nickel current feeders were used with defined flow field structure. The KOH solutions (0.1 or 1 M) were pumped separately to anode and cathode side with the flow rate of 25 mL min^{-1} and the solution was heated so that the temperature at the outlet of the cell was $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

The MEA performance was analyzed by measuring load curves from 1.5 to 2.2 V with 0.05 V step size using potentiostat/galvanostat Autolab PGSTAT101 equipped with 10 A booster and FRA32M module allowing for EIS.

A stability test was performed at constant current density of 250 mA cm^{-2} in 1 M KOH solution at $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The PIM-1 content in the SEBS-DABCO/PIM-1 blend was 50 wt%. Stability at constant current density was coupled with EIS measurement to obtain additional information on the cell performance.

EIS was used to evaluate resistances of the electrolytic cell at voltages of 0, 1.5, and 1.8 V. The maximum amplitude of the perturbing signal used was 10 mV. Measurements at 0 V were performed in a frequency range of 65 kHz–100 Hz, while impedance spectra measured at 1.5 and 1.8 V were obtained in a frequency range 20 kHz–0.1 Hz. The equivalent electrical circuit used to evaluate the parameters of the electrolytic cell consists of an inductance element to simulate the influence of the connecting cables in series with resistance standing for cell ohmic resistance (R_s) connected in series with parallelly connected R_p -CPE blocks representing the polarization resistance of the electrodes (R_p) and double layer capacity at the electrode-electrolyte boundary (CPE). Either one or two R_p -CPE blocks were used in dependence on the number of the time constants observed from EIS spectra. Scheme of the equivalent electrical circuit is shown in Figure S5 (Supporting Information).

Other Characterizations: The degree of chloromethylation of the synthesized polymers was investigated using NMR (400 MHz, Bruker). For the NMR analysis, the polymers were dissolved in CDCl_3 . For measuring the density of the pristine and blend membranes of PIM-1 and CM-SEBS, the membranes were casted and dried first. The weight and area of three membranes were measured for each membrane type, and the density was calculated using the basic formula ($d = M/V$), where d represents density, M is the mass, and V is the volume.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

anion exchange membrane water electrolyzer, gas permeability, hydroxide conducting ionomer binder, PIM-1, SEBS-DABCO

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